

NOTES

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL VALUES AND COMPOSITION OF SEED OILS

Sl. no.	Oil	Iodine %	Sap. value	Fatty acid composition (%)								
				16:0	16:1	18:0	18:1	18:2	18:3	20:0	Others	
1.	<i>A. fraxinifolius</i> , Wight and Arn. (Caesalpinaceae)	8	70	192	18.8	—	3.4	76.3	1.5	—	—	—
2.	<i>C. equisetifolia</i> , Linn. (Casuarinaceae)	10	145	191	9.61	—	3.6	8.32	78.5	—	—	—
3.	<i>L. theroili</i> , Linn. (Lythraceae)	8	120	194	23.5	—	2.9	30.5	22.2	20.8	—	—
4.	<i>P. juliflora</i> , D.C. (Mimosaceae)	10	98	195	27.1	—	3.0	35.2	27.7	7	—	—
5.	<i>B. defusa</i> , Linn. (Nyctaginaceae)	10	50	195	98.8	1.36	2.76	52.0	2.76	—	—	22:0, 1.81
6.	<i>D. cordifolia</i> , Roxb. (Ebenaceae)	3	49	210	40.25	—	5.71	13.15	14.85	3.66	4.23	10:0, 2.82, 12:0, 13.82, 14:0, 1.76

Experimental

Infrared spectra (film) were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer and ultraviolet spectra (methanol) with a Beckman DK-2A spectrophotometer. Glc analyses were carried out with a Perkin-Elmer 154 instrument equipped with DEGS column. Tlc studies were done on silica gel plates. A 20% aqueous solution of perchloric acid was used as the spraying agent.

Seeds were cleaned and analysed as reported³. Methanolysis of the oil with H₂SO₄ as catalyst yielded methyl esters of the fatty acids, which were analysed by glc. In general, the esters were examined by various tlc techniques prior to glc analysis to ascertain the presence or absence of unusual acids.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank to Prof. S. A. A. Zaidi, Chairman, Department of Chemistry, for facilities. One of the authors (M.T.S.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi. Thanks are also due to ICAR-USDA for financial assistance.

References

1. M. T. SAREED, A. RAUF and S. M. OSMAN, *J. Oil Technol. Assoc.*, 1987, **19**, 86; S. M. OSMAN, F. AHMAD and I. AHMAD in "Minor Seed Oils: New Sources of Vegetable Oils in Oil Seeds and their Utilization", eds. R. K. SURI and K. C. MATHUR, Rohini Publishing House, Dehradun, 1984, p. 113.
2. "Official and Tentative Methods of the American Oil Chemists' Society", 3rd ed., AOCS, Champaign, 1973.
3. F. AHMAD, M. U. AHMAD, I. AHMAD, A. A. ANSARI and S. M. OSMAN, *Fette Seifen Anstrichm.*, 1978, **80**, 190.

Simultaneous Extraction and Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium(v) in Geological Materials with 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-pyrazolone

H. C. ARORA

Department of Atomic Energy, West Block VII, R. K. Puram, New Delhi-110 066

Manuscript received 6 October 1988, revised 1 September 1989, accepted 22 January 1990

THE present communication describes the extractive spectrophotometric determination of vanadium(v) present in geochemical samples using the reagent 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-benzoyl-5-pyrazolone (PMBP).

Experimental

The reagent PMBP was prepared by the literature procedure¹. Solutions of the required concentrations were prepared in chloroform-butanol (4:1) mixture. A stock solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) of vanadium was prepared from ammonium metavanadate in 1 M H₂SO₄ and diluted to 100 and 10 µg ml⁻¹.

A Varian 634 double beam spectrophotometer was used for absorbance measurements.

Procedure: Standard vanadium(v) solution (100 µg ml⁻¹) was shaken with 5 ml of 0.1M PMBP solution (5 ml) at pH 3 in a separating funnel for 5 min. The absorbance of the extracted complex against the reagent blank was measured at 490 nm. The effect of diverse ions was studied by adding their standard solutions into vanadium standard and extracting the mixture at pH 3 with PMBP solution. Analysis of vanadium in some real samples are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that 5 ml of 0.1M PMBP solution in chloroform-butanol (4:1) is sufficient to extract 100 µg vanadium(v) in the pH range 2.5–4.5,

TABLE 1—ANALYSIS OF VANADIUM IN NATURAL SAMPLES BY THE PROPOSED METHOD

Sample	Volume taken ml	V found ppb	V added μ g	V found ppb
Distilled water	500	*	5.0	9
Tap water	500	*	10.0	19
			5.0	9
			10.0	19
Water sample			10.0	59
JDF/7/26	500	41	20.0	77
JDF/8/32	250	472.8		
	500	468.6		
JDF/8/3	250	33.5		
	500	35.5		
BSL/21	500	<10		
	500	<10		
MJN/1/3	250	130		
	500	128		
Rock sample	% V_2O_5	0.022		
BSL-16/11		(0.021)%		
BSL-16/12	% V_2O_5	0.020		
		(0.019)%		

*Not detectable.

Values within the parenthesis were obtained by BPHA method².

beyond which the extraction of vanadium falls. Mixture of chloroform and butanol (4:1) was found to be the best compromise to obtain optimum sensitivity and stability. Large amounts (50 mg) of Cr^{VI} if reduced to Cr^{III} do not interfere. 10 mg each of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Al^{III} , Pt^{IV} and U^{VI} do not interfere. Fe^{III} and Ti^{IV} are removed as insoluble hydroxide after leaching the fused alkaline melt of soil/rock samples with water prior to the determination of V^V . Fe^{III} may also be masked with dilute solution of potassium hydrogen phosphate. Tolerance limit of Mo^{VI} and W^{VI} is 250 and 50 μ g respectively.

References

1. B. S. JENSEN, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1959, 13, 1668, 1890.
2. R. C. SARKAR and B. L. RAO, "Extraction-Spectrophotometric Determination of Vanadium with N-Benzoyl-N-Phenyl-hydroxylamine (BPHA)", Analytical Chemistry Division, BARO, Bombay, unpublished report.

Polarographic Studies of Chromate Ion in Different Media for Trace Analysis

P. SHARMA* and C. RAWAT

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, University of Jodhpur, Jodhpur-342 001

Manuscript received 6 September 1988, revised 23 October 1989, accepted 22 January 1990

DETERMINATIONS of trace metals pose challenging problems which are of vital significance when present more than the prescribed limits in water and other media¹. Among them cadmium, lead, mercury and chromium excel the rest due to their high toxicity. Some of these, viz. lead and chromium are known to be insidious poisons for human

and other organisms². It is therefore desirable to monitor their concentrations in different matrices. A voltammetric method for the determination of chromium in the presence of ammonium tartrate buffer has been published previously by us³. Though, the method enables the simultaneous determination of Cd, Cr, Pb and Zn, but it requires precise control of pH and use of expensive reagents. Concerning our search for a faster, simpler and less expensive method, we tried a number of supporting electrolytes. Among them, sodium hydroxide solution proved to be the best.

Hume and Kolthoff⁴ studied polarographic behaviour of chromium in potassium cyanide medium. Sankaranarayanan *et al.*⁵ investigated electrochemical reduction of hexavalent chromium. Jindal *et al.*⁶ developed a differential pulse polarographic (dpp) method for the estimation of chromium in presence of zinc. The authors propose a routine dpp method for trace analysis of chromium in industrial effluents.

Experimental

A PAR 174-A polarographic analyser along with a drop timer was used for polarographic studies. D.C. and dp polarograms were recorded by a RE 0074 X-Y recorder. Natural drop time was employed for dc polarography. Pulse parameters in dpp were as follows: pulse amplitude, 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; clock time of pulse, 1 sec. All the potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (sce). A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode. A Shimadzu AA-630 atomic absorption/flame spectrophotometer was also used for sample analyses.

All chemicals used were of reagent grade. Synthetic water samples were prepared containing 0.5 ppm Pb^{II} , 1.0 ppm each of Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} and Fe^{III} with varying concentrations of Cr^{VI} (0.094–7.092 ppm). Industrial effluent samples were collected from different selected points of Basni area. The solutions were deaerated by bubbling purified nitrogen for 20 min prior to measurements.

All experiments were made in an air conditioned room at a temperature of $26 \pm 1^\circ$.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic reduction of Cr^{VI} was studied in ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer, phosphate buffer and sodium hydroxide medium.

Chromate ion in presence of ammonia-ammonium chloride (pH 10.0) buffer displayed a polarographic wave with a half-wave potential ($E_{1/2}$) of -0.28 V. It also showed dp peak at -0.30 V. This medium could not be used for quantitation purposes due to the saturation of the purge nitrogen gas with supporting electrolyte as bubbled gas depleted the solution of volatile ammonia which resulted in decreasing pH of analysing sample followed by a shift in peak potential.